

**THE MECHANISMS OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE ON THE
BASIS OF INTERACTIVE TEACHING METHODS**

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Abstract: This article discusses the use of modern methods in teaching English.

Key words: method, translation method, oral method, psychological method, indirect method, reading method, suggestopedia, socratic seminar, discussion style, ingenuity style, remembering style, mimic style, ordering style, role playing style and kahoot.

From the first days of independence, our country began to pay great attention to teaching foreign languages, especially English. Including the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-4947, December 10, 2012 "On Measures to Improve the System of Foreign Language Learning" - Implementation of the tasks defined in the decisions No. 2909 is one of the urgent issues facing foreign language education.

In the book of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Serving for the happiness and prosperity of our motherland and its great future is the highest happiness", the following opinion is expressed about the importance of teaching foreign languages to the young generation at the level of state policy: "We have started major works in terms of substance. In particular, we made a special decision in this regard in 2012. In this short period of time, these works are yielding positive results. If we continue the work we have started, if we are lucky, we will achieve an "explosion effect" in this regard as well."

In teaching a foreign language, first of all, it is necessary to form the speech mechanism based on the formation of speech skills (here we are talking about the formation of the speech mechanism of a foreign language) and conduct methodical work on the development of speech skills.

In the decision of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to strengthen the material and technical base of higher education institutions and fundamentally improve the quality of training of highly qualified specialists" dated May 20, 2011 PQ 1533 further strengthening and modernization of the material and technical base of teaching foreign languages on the basis of doing this, the task of training personnel who know foreign languages well and can communicate freely in their field was determined.

The main goal of teaching a foreign language at all stages of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to form the communicative competence of students in a foreign language in order to carry out activities in everyday, scientific and professional fields in a multicultural world.

It is known that foreign languages are determined by the characteristics of the educational subject, the nature of the teaching process, and a specific theory that underpins the pedagogic-didactic system. The purpose, tasks, content, methods, principles, means, conditions and requirements of the subject of foreign languages taught in general secondary education and secondary special vocational education of continuous education are fundamentally different from other subjects. This subject requires the formation of knowledge, skills and skills necessary for special communication in young students.

In the initial learning of the English language, the initial educational processes are organized in order to develop the student's speech by using situational and educational games. Therefore, it is necessary to select and sort didactic games used in learning English. Achieving students' activity in English classes depends on the right choice of teaching methods and methods. According to the analysis of

methodological practices, with the help of certain methods and methods, students' cognitive activity is carried out in 2 ways: to increase their interest in science, to ensure students' independence. In the process of learning a foreign language, students' enthusiasm for independent learning increases in a lesson organized on the basis of non-traditional educational technologies. They will have a creative approach to mastering educational materials, professional training, skills and abilities will be improved, as a result, the quality and effectiveness of English language education will increase. Currently, improving the quality of English language education in general secondary schools and using interactive methods is one of the most urgent issues today, and effective use of the Internet system is also considered a desirable task.

The science of teaching is illuminated by the science of methodology, the word "methodike" comes from Greek and means "a set of methods for doing something according to the purpose". The method of teaching a foreign language means the set of activities of the teacher and the student, which ensures the achievement of the practical, general educational, educational and developmental goals of teaching a foreign language.

The term method is used in the sense of "a set of educational methods" and "the direction of education".

Currently, there are a number of methods of teaching foreign languages in the world, which are used by teachers in a domesticated manner. Some of such methods are:

- translation method (mainly used in learning foreign languages, words and grammatical rules are memorized);
- oral method (based on the system of rearranging the teacher's monologue and answering questions on the text);
- psychological method (based on finding associations between the word and the concept expressed by the word);

- indirect teaching method (used without reference to foreign language, native language or any other language, without using translation at all);

-reading method (the more text a student reads in the target language, the more he learns the features, grammatical rules, and sentence patterns of this language, and thus the skills of understanding, speaking, and writing develop.

At the same time, the methodology known as "suggestopedia" has developed widely in many countries of the world today. This method, which is related to intensification of education and hypnosis, has been evaluated in different ways, criticized and applauded. However, its results are surprising. Pedagogues teaching on the basis of Suggestopedia receive special training. The maximum favorable conditions were created for learners to quickly learn a new language. Each student is convinced that he has extraordinary linguistic abilities, the lesson is conducted with the help of movement and games, as well as musical effects to facilitate the reception of the material, multimedia tools are constantly used. When using this method, the speed of language learning increases 40-50 times, because the number of words and sentences memorized per day is much higher than the numbers in the usual method.

- "Socratic seminar" this method is based on the teaching method of the famous philosopher Socrates by asking countless questions. The teacher gives the students a text covering the required topic and time to prepare. The teacher will find out to what extent the students have understood the topic by asking a series of questions.

"Philosophical chair" method is similar to a debate. Students will be given the main topic and questions. They can agree, disagree or remain neutral. This method is based on students having lively discussions with each other and learning new things from each other. Each student takes turns sitting on a chair in the center and expressing their opinions. Then the debate begins.

Foreign languages are determined by the nature of the subject, the nature of the teaching process and the specific theory that underpins the pedagogical-didactic

system. Foreign languages differ from other subjects in terms of their goals, tasks, content, methods, principles, tools, conditions and requirements. This subject requires the formation of special communicative knowledge, knowledge and skills in students.

I. A. Bim describes the content of teaching and the content of the subject separately. In his opinion, the content of teaching determines the process of reading and teaching. It is necessary to organize the linguistic material from the methodical side in order to achieve the goal set through the teaching content faster.

N. D. Galskovo said that the process of teaching a foreign language differs from other educational subjects by its complexity and complexity. Concepts such as modeling, managing, discussing the process of effective acquisition of foreign languages, as well as differentiating the special features of the subject "Foreign language" from other subjects are organized in language didactics.

Today, in the process of teaching foreign languages, according to the social order of the state, English or a foreign language is used for the following purposes in the world. They are: EGP (English for general purposes); EAP (English for academic purposes) - English for academic purposes; ESP (English for specific purposes) - English for special purposes (related to medicine, technology, engineering and other fields); EST (English for science and technology) - English for scientific and technical purposes; EOP (English for occupational purposes) consists of English for professional purposes by field. In the process of learning English, you can come across such terms. They are: EFL (English as a foreign language) English or another foreign language as a 2nd foreign language (if the mother tongue is spoken in the family circle, but learning another foreign language available in the environment).

The goals, educational content, principles, tasks and technologies of foreign language teaching are deeply discussed by scientists and researchers in methodical literature. In the 50s and 60s of the 20th century, there were practical or

communicative purposes, educational purposes, and training purposes, but at the end of the 20th century, a developing purpose appeared in addition to these purposes. . According to the Common European Competencies (CEFR) document of the Council of Europe, the main goal of learning English is the formation of communicative competence. This communicative competence is characterized by levels (A, A1, A1+B, B1, B1+, C, C1+) consisting of several components. This competency also includes several sub-competencies. They are: linguistic, sociolinguistic, sociocultural, strategic, discursive, social competencies.

There are a number of examples of the following methodology for the formation of the ability to speak English at the "Initial level" of English language learners:

-Ask and answer method. Pupils answer the teacher's and classmates' questions and ask each other questions.

-Imagination and drawing (Describe and draw) style. Here students should work in groups. 1st student looks at the picture given by the teacher and begins to describe it. Student 2 should draw it.

-Discussion (Discussion) style. Pupils work in different groups and in pairs. They conduct discussions on the topic given to them.

-Ingenuity (Guessing) style. Teachers and students get some information about the new topic. The students of the class have to find it with resourcefulness in the form of questions and answers.

-Remembering (Remembering) method. Students should close their eyes and describe the pictures given by the teacher or the equipment in the classroom.

-Mimic style (Miming). Pupils describe the things given by the teacher with different facial expressions. And the students of the class have to find them.

-Ordering style. The teacher instructs the students to make new sentences in the sequence of letters of the alphabet. Pupils make words related to each letter from the letter that ends with that letter.

-Role playing style. Pupils show something or something related to the topic with role-plays in different ways.-Jigsaw style. It is better for students to work in groups in this way. The teacher distributes papers on which sentences with incomplete sentences related to the topic are written to the groups. The students of the group create a text by arranging them in the correct order. Finally, they express their opinions about this text.

It should be recognized that as the world moves to a new stage of development in the age of information technologies of the 21st century, it is becoming difficult for people to imagine life without modern technologies. If we connect these technologies directly and indirectly to the educational process, we can use different methods to determine the extent to which students have understood the new content. It is known that some students hesitate to ask the teacher for the answer to a question that remains abstract for them. For example, in the same situation, if we use the "Kahoot" program, all students can be covered in the same lesson. How to use Kahoot is as follows: Each student is required to use the Internet on their smartphone effectively, and they simultaneously enter the Kahoot message on the Internet. After connecting all the students to the Internet, performing the necessary actions on their smartphones (entering the name and e-mail) and gathering in a group, the teacher will press the [start] button and monitor the game. In this case, students must complete interesting conditions and tests in English on a new topic within a limited time. At the end of this technological method, the name of the student who is the most active and thoroughly absorbed the lesson will be displayed on the program screen and will be encouraged by the teacher. After the new topic is reinforced in this way, all students will get answers to their questions. Based on this method of teaching, it is possible to increase students' interest in English. Students who participate in the class look forward to the lessons and complete the homework assignments on time without any difficulties. As a result, their ability to master the English language is increasing.

In conclusion, it should be said that non-traditionally organized lessons remain in the memory of pupils and students for a long time. Interactive methods make boring and familiar lessons interesting for students. Interactive methods and new modern technologies allow students to feel confident in their independent life, to quickly adapt to new conditions, and to acquire the necessary set of modern knowledge, skills and skills that allow them to find optimal solutions to complex problems. The use of modern interactive methods in teaching English has a positive effect in today's continuous education system.

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